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Research Article

Comparative study of the effects of Type I and Type II Diabetes on Human Health using Statistical Models

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Abstract:

This study compared the impacts the two types of diabetes known as type I and type II on human health using probit and binary regression. The data used in this work was obtained from the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (2021) in Port Harcourt. The study employed chi-square, p-value, goodness of fit test, and analysis of variance. It was observed that type II diabetes was more dangerous than type I. In addition, type II diabetes has more negative effects on the patients than type I. It was also found that both type I and type II are dangerous to health. It was also revealed that the probit model was better than the binary logistic model.

Keywords: Type I And Type II Diabetes, Binary, Probit, p-value.

Introduction

The incidence of diabetes is on the rise all over the world. As stated by World Health Organization (2016) report, that, there have been more than 36 million deaths as a result of non-communicable and long-lasting (chronic) diseases in the universal range. Also, diabetes ranked fourth which accounts for 3% in 2008. During the ending of 2014, the figure of people with diabetes in the global angle reached 422 million and this accounted for about 8.5% of the total population. Recently, the percentage of deaths due to diabetes has progressively increased as a proportion of all deaths caused by chronic diseases. Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disease branded by high blood glucose. It is long-lasting in nature and can be seen as a lifelong disease, it is one of the main non-communicable and chronic diseases that can result in various problems, such as diabetic nephropathy, hypertension, diabetic foot and coronary heart disease. Existing diabetes data and trends, estimated that the number of people with diabetes worldwide will reach 366 million by 2030. Currently, the proportion of the possible population with diabetes in Chinese adults is as high as 15.5, and 60.7% of these individuals had not formerly received a diagnosis of prediabetes (Siyu *et al.*, 2019).

Categories of Diabetes

This diabetes types are dependent on the circumstances that the disease causes in human body. A classification of diabetes was developed by the American Diabetes Association known as Type I diabetes, type II, gestational diabetes, etc.

Type I diabetes

Type I diabetes is known as that which depends on insulin and it is a chronic disease that arises when the pancreas, releases little or no amount of insulin to the body system. The Insulin is a hormone that imports sugar into the cells for energy production.

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It controls blood sugar level, it also, allows the use or absorbing of sugar by the body system from the blood system. When the body resist insulin or the body cells fails to use it well, it results to Hyperinsulinemia and is related to type 2 diabetes. Numerous factors, such as infection and genetics with certain viruses, can cause type I diabetes. While type 1 diabetes usually occurs in puberty and childhood, nonetheless adults are also vulnerable to it.

Type 2 diabetes

According to Parastoo and Ahmad (2016), is a disease that does not depend on insulin. It is also known as an adult diabetes. It is one of the most common types of diabetes and it constitute about 90 percent of the patient. In type 2 diabetes, the body produces insulin, but the insulin which is produced by the pancreas is not enough for the body or the body does not use the produced insulin properly. When there is not enough insulin or the body does not use insulin, the glucose (sugar) in the body, cannot move to the body's cells resulting in glucose accumulation. This process endangers the body. It also results each time one's blood sugar is so high. It is highly regrettable that there is no cure for this disease, nonetheless with regular exercise, healthy diet and keeping fit, one can be sustained for a long while. If diet and exercise are not enough, you need medication or insulin treatment. Umar, *et al.* (2018) applied multivariate analysis processes even Fisher's method in studying the tackling of Diabetic patients in Damaturu, Nigeria. Just recently, Onu *et al.* (2020) considered the Binary Logistic and Poisson Regression Models for Diabetic Patients with Dichotomous and Non-Dichotomous Predictors, it compared Poisson and Binary logistic regressions of type I and type II diabetes patients for dichotomous and non-dichotomous predictors. It was observed that the binary logistic model was significant while the Poisson model was not and the type I and type II diabetes have negative effects on the patients. All these studies fell short of using Binary and Probit regressions in studying the effects of type 1 and type 2 diabetes on Human beings in Nigeria in the year 2021. It was against this backdrop this work was presented. The work is aimed at comparing these two generalized linear models on the effects of type I and type II diabetes on human beings in Nigeria. Morteza *et al.* (2013) associated the conditional logistic regression with neural networks, as such the latter have better predicted albuminuria in type II diabetes. Thirugnanam *et al.* (2012) bettered the prediction in diabetes through fuzzy neural networks. Marateb *et al.* (2014), have offered cross intelligent systems for the detection of microalbuminuria in patients with type 2 diabetes without measuring the urinary albumin. Javad *et al.* (2014) proposed a method based on automatic learning on type II diabetes to regulate blood sugar.

Materials and Methods

Probit Regression

This is a member of the family of generalized linear models, like the logistic regression, its link function is given as:

$$f(\mu_r) = \Phi^{-1}(p) \quad (1)$$

it uses an inverse normal link function given in (1) above. In the binary case, Y can assume only the values 0,1, our interest is to know how a predictor is related to the probability that Y=1, but we cannot use the probability itself as a function as a result of the following reasons;

1. Probability can only be 0 or 1, that is to say, the right-hand-side of the equation can vary from $-\infty$ to ∞
2. The relationship between probability and the predictors is not linear, rather, it is sigmoidal (S-shaped).

As a result, we need a function of the probability that converts a probability into a value that runs from $-\infty$ to ∞ and also, has a linear relationship with predictors. Hence the logistic and Probit regression do these two things perfectly. See Karen Grace-Martin.

Logistic Regression Model

The logistic regression which is one of the generalized linear models is given as seen in Parastoo and Ahmad (2016) and recently as seen by Onu *et al.* (2022) as

$$\text{Logit}(p) = \ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \alpha + \beta_1 x_{1i} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ki}, i = 1, \dots, n \quad (2)$$

The link function of a logit regression is $f(\mu_r) = \ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right)$

Where

$$p = p_r(Y_i = 1) \quad \text{and}$$

$$p = p_r\left(Y_i = \frac{1}{X}\right) = \frac{e^{\mu + \beta_1 x_{1i} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ki}}}{1 + e^{\mu + \beta_1 x_{1i} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ki}}} \quad (3)$$

Logistic regression is similar to linear regression but the difference is that their coefficients are different. The linear regression minimizes the sum of square errors, while the logistic regression maximizes the probability that an event will occur. We use the F and t-statistics for linear regression, while we use chi-square and Wald for logistic regression.

It is generally given as

$$\log\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \mu + \sum \beta X \quad (4)$$

X is a vector of independent variables,
 β is the vector of estimated parameters,
 P= is the likely outcomes or events

Results and Discussion

Probit Analysis

Parameter Estimates							
	Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	Z	Sig.	95% CI	
						LB	UB
PROBIT ^a	type2	-.033	.014	-2.405	.016	-.060	-.006
	Intercept	-1.270	.287	-4.432	.000	-1.556	-.983

a. PROBIT model: PROBIT(p) = Intercept + BX

Chi-Square Tests					
			Chi-Square	df ^b	Sig.
PROBIT	Pearson Goodness-of-Fit Test		19.011	22	.645 ^a

a. Since the significance level is greater than .150, no heterogeneity factor is used in the calculation of confidence limits.
 b. Statistics based on individual cases differ from statistics based on aggregated cases.

PROBIT gender of type2 WITH type1
 /LOG NONE
 /MODEL PROBIT
 /PRINT FREQ CI
 /CRITERIA P(.15) ITERATE(20) STEPLIMIT(.1).

Parameter Estimates							
	Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	Z	Sig.	95% CI	
						LB	UB
PROBIT ^a	type1	-.040	.019	-2.083	.037	-.077	-.002
	Intercept	-1.237	.338	-3.660	.000	-1.575	-.899

a. PROBIT model: PROBIT(p) = Intercept + BX

Chi-Square Tests					
			Chi-Square	df ^b	Sig.
PROBIT	Pearson Goodness-of-Fit Test		19.943	22	.587 ^a

a. Since the significance level is greater than .150, no heterogeneity factor is used in the calculation of confidence limits.
 b. Statistics based on individual cases differ from statistics based on aggregated cases.

Logistic Regression: gender versus type 1, type 2

* WARNING * When the data are in the Response/Frequency format, the Residuals versus fits the plot is unavailable.

Deviance Table

Source	DF	Adj Dev	Adj Mean	Chi-Square	P-Value
Regression	2	6.776	3.388	6.78	0.034
type 1	1	15.616	1.616	1.62	0.204
type 2	1	1.932	1.932	1.93	0.165
Error	21	26.495	1.262		
Total	23	33.271			

Model Summary

Deviance R-Sq	Deviance R-Sq (adj)	AIC
20.37%	14.35%	32.50

Coefficients

Term	Coef	SE Coef	VIF
Constant	2.68	1.34	
type 1	-0.0598	0.0561	1.12
type 2	-0.0716	0.0548	1.12

Regression Equation

$$P(1) = \frac{\exp(Y')}{1 + \exp(Y')}$$

$$Y' = 2.68 - 0.0598 \text{ type 1} - 0.0716 \text{ type 2}$$

Goodness-of-Fit Tests

Test	DF	Chi-Square	P-Value
Deviance	21	26.50	0.188
Pearson	21	23.82	0.302
Hosmer-Lemeshow	8	5.54	0.698

Discussion

The type II Diabetes for the year 2018 for Probit regression has a Chi-square value of 19.011 with a significant level of 0.645. Since this significance level is greater than 150, it means that there is no heterogeneity factor used in the calculation of confidence limits. The scatter plot shows a negative relationship between type II diabetes and the human being (male or female). The regression of type I diabetes has a chi-square value of 19.943 and a significance level of 0.587. Also, there is no heterogeneity factor used in the calculation of confidence limits. The scatter plot shows a negative relationship between type I diabetes and the human being (male or female). The scatter plot of the type II and type I diabetes differs in that, type I formed a cluster below -1.50 probit value and a point above the cluster at -1.23. while the cluster for type II was formed below -1.4. The binary regression revealed that the regression equation is significant with a p-value of 0.034. The adjusted mean square shows that type 2 diabetes is more active and severe than type I. The model was only able to explain 20.37% of the variations in the response (Gender). It has an AIC value of 32.50 and the VIF shows that there is no presence of multicollinearity in the data. The regression-fitted model shows that type II diabetes has more negative effects on the individual than type I, but generally, all the diabetes types studied had negative contributions to the genders.

Conclusion

The study concludes that both models were good in the study of the effects of diabetes on human beings in Nigeria, but the probit regression proved to be the better model, majorly as a result of its simplicity. Also, the two types of diabetes were found to have negative effects on the human beings, irrespective of the gender.

Recommendations

The study recommends the following to statisticians medical researchers and the general public:

1. Health workers should take the treatment of type I diabetes seriously to avoid going into the danger zone of type II.
2. The patients should adhere strictly to the advice of the health workers to avoid the severity of the illness.
3. The general public should ensure regular medical checkups to ascertain their health status on time, for this will solve the problem of diabetes if appropriate measures are taken.
4. To researchers, the study shows that probit regression is better used than binary logistic regression.

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